

SURFACE AREA CORRECTION (SAC): APPROACH TO REDUCE EMISSION FACTOR FROM OIL PALM PLANTATION ON TROPICAL PEATLAND

Marshall Kana Samuel^{1*} and Stephanie Lorna Evers²

¹Soil Science, Water & Fertilizer Research Centre, MARDI Saratok, Sarawak.

²School of Natural Sciences & Psychology, Liverpool John Moores University, Liverpool United Kingdom.

**E-mail: marshall@mardi.gov.my*

INTRODUCTION

In the past decades, the design of oil palm (OP) plantation layout has turned into an important industry topic with the aim of maximising yield and productivity. The plantation monoculture resulting from conversion of forest ecosystem to plantation adversely affect species richness and subsequent maturation of plantations can also provide unwitting areas of rehabilitation through unwedded microsites within OP or frond piling [1]. Each microsite has distinct characteristics depending on standard planting density and management practices. These attributes are hypothesised to affect site-specific peat property heterogeneity. While partitioning the heterotrophic (HR) and autotrophic (AR) contributions of soil respiration (SR) by roots availability has been studied extensively, those studies do not capture the heterogeneity within these zones, nor are the contribution of these areas accounted for in terms of up-scaled emissions estimated for entire plantations. Furthermore, the implication for informed policy making is significant. In 2011, the US EPA [2] undertook peer reviews from several experts in tropical peat research to discuss the usage of a default OP on peat emissions factor (EF) value. While this resulted in a determination of 95 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, this remains largely inflated compared to the 40 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ proposed by IPCC 2007 [3]. Thus, in order to address uncertainties in calculating the EF of drained OP on tropical peatland, while much of this ambiguity lies in emissions within the first 5 years of conversion, varied peat generation and intra-site heterogeneity also requires full accounting.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The particular interest of this study is towards active areas described by microsites (Figure 1(a)) with the greatest carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission was observed at Under Canopy (UC) microsite and differed to Frond Pile (FP) microsite. The proposed method of Surface Area Correction (SAC) was calculated based on common planting density of OP across tropical peatland in triangular planting (Figure 1(b)) in accordance to 160 palms per hectare, which has been commonly exercised on tropical peatland. The steps to calculate SAC are as follows: First, calculate the area covered by UC using the area of the circle with radius (R_{op}) value of

3.0 m that represents effective SR based on oil palm root, as proposed by [4]. The value of UC was 28.28 m² per palm. Next, calculate the FP value by assuming that the fronds piles were located side-by-side to the palm. Assuming FP microsite was rectangular in shape and subtracted by the UC area and given the length of hypotenuse for planting density was 8.5 m and the length of one side was half of UC that of 1.5 m, the other side can be calculated by using Pythagorean Theorem. After that, using UC and FP values, calculations of Harvesting Path (HP) and Far from Palm (FF) were made by assuming that both microsities shared similar area of rectangular shape. Therefore, the value of HP was calculated by deducting 10,000 m² or 1.0 hectare from UC and FP values and later, divided by two. Hence, the proportion of microsities area were 0.224, 0.452, 0.1, and 0.224 for HP, UC, FP, and FF, respectively, which led to 1.0 or 100%.

Figure 1. (a) Oil palm plantation that classified into different microsities namely Harvesting Path (HP), Under Canopy (UC), Frond Piles (FP) and Far from Palm (FP). **(b)** Typical planting density of oil palm plantation on tropical peatland in equilateral triangle planting density of 8.5 m x 8.5 m x 8.5 m

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here, several strategies have been proposed to reduce EF from OP on drained tropical peatland using SAC. The first approach is to reduce the number of palms. As the SAC had been based on 160 palms per hectare, limiting up to 143 palms per hectare based on 9.0 m x 9.0 m x 9.0 m planting density may enhance the coefficients of FF and HP microsities, while decreasing FP and UC. In explaining the reduction, UC microsite was used due to its greatest CO₂ emission, in comparison to the others. From the calculations, EF decreased by 11% from 157 to 140 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. This reduction is attributable to the entire entities of SR (AR and HR) in UC, where the SAC factor decreased from 0.452 to 0.404. The second approach is through conversion of FF and HP microsities to FP, whereby FP in this study recorded the lowest CO₂

emission, when compared to other microsites. Hence, if FF, HP or both microsites are converted to FP, reduction of EFs by 1%, 5%, and 6% can be estimated.

Figure 2. CO₂ emissions from study sites with purposed default emissions factor. Dash line represents EPA (2014) purposed default emission factor that of 95 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, while solid line represents IPCC (2011) purposed default emission factor that of 40 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹

CONCLUSION

Consideration of these microsites with area surface correction is integral and allows one to accurately estimate the amount of gas emission. This provides the interim key to information for mitigation measures in reducing carbon emission from matured OP, for example, by using the SAC as proposed in this work. Nevertheless, as the estimation from 35 to 157 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ and indeed within to the default value proposed by EPA and IPCC, with two sampling cycles may be insufficient to provide a holistic approach for the overall estimation in light of geographical area. Therefore, further measurement in long term is required.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This 2015/16 campaign was supported by Malaysian Agricultural Research & Development Institute (MARDI) through PhD Scholarship at University Nottingham Malaysia Campus.

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